

R3PACK

R3PACK - REDUCE, REUSE, RETHINK PACKAGING TOWARDS NOVEL FIBRE-BASED PACKAGING AND REUSE SCHEMES

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.3 “What if scenarios and policy recommendations” presents forward-looking policy scenarios and recommendations based on empirical results from the R3PACK project, which designed and tested on field large-scale reusable packaging loops and tested fibre-based packaging alternatives on production line for food applications. The aim is to help European and national authorities design coherent regulatory, financial and governance frameworks capable of accelerating the transition away from single-use plastics.

The analysis builds on four years of demonstrations across retailers, manufacturers, logistics providers and partners. R3PACK’s experience shows that, although technical obstacles remain, both reuse and fibre-based substitution could be technically feasible for a significant proportion of products. Their scalability depends on coordinated action across regulation, financial support, infrastructure, consumer engagement and standardisation.

Technical insights indicate that reuse systems can operate effectively once logistics, washing, IT tools and packaging formats are harmonised, although challenges remain in plastic resin suitability, allergen-safe washing and IT integration. Fibre-based single used packaging solutions demonstrate strong potential for specific categories such as pastry dough or savoury biscuits, but broader deployment is constrained by barrier performance, machinability limits, and higher material costs.

Economic findings show that both models require scale and financial support to reach competitiveness.

For reuse systems, costs of production are increased as the production efficiency decreases (loss of pace, smaller batches, need for more labour and storage space). In addition, new costs must be considered related to the reuse loop (collecting, sorting, washing, transport). However, a major lever is the increase in volumes and the expansion of the product range available. This would lead to a greater consumer adoption, higher return rates, and lower logistics and washing costs per unit, ultimately improving the model’s overall viability. For fibre-based packaging, purchase of paper-based packaging remains 2–5 times higher than plastics, and production costs are higher as speed is reduced, requiring financial support for R&D and industrial upgrades.

Therefore, 3 key levers need to be worked on to deliver competitive costs in reuse and substitution:

- **Engaging consumers is the primary lever for enabling solutions to scale**, yet this lever is overlooked by brands, NGOs and regulators. Behavioural studies show that adoption increases significantly when consumers perceive a **clear economic benefit**, supported by **environmental** advantages and **convenient and desirable** packaging solutions. Communication strategies that clearly convey these benefits, combined with product ranges that reach critical mass and offer affordable options or direct financial incentives, are essential to accelerate large-scale behavioural adoption.
- **Investing in R&D** to improve packaging solutions (both reuse and paper-based), and to adapt existing lines to paper materials or reusable packaging, to reach single use plastic efficiency. In addition, R&D investment should be directed towards plastic washing centers to enable the scale-up of reusable plastic packaging model.
- **Increasing packaging volumes** will decrease purchasing costs of packaging (paper-based and reusable) thanks to economies of scale. More over, it allows for optimization of the reuse logistic system therefore optimizes the economic and environmental model.

Based on these learnings, the deliverable develops three “what-if” scenarios describing alternative trajectories for Europe’s packaging transition:

1. **Business as usual**, with fragmented regulations, limited packaging availability, slow consumer adoption and minimal market penetration (~5% reuse; 10–15% fibre).

2. **Collaborative regional initiatives**, where shared standards, joint investments and coordinated communication enable moderate uptake (15–20% reuse; 20–25% fibre).
3. **Fully integrated European solutions**, where harmonised EU rules, standardised packaging, interoperable deposit systems and large-scale infrastructure unlock widespread transformation (30–40% reuse; 30–45% fibre).

Across scenarios, a clear message emerges; meaningful progress requires coherent, predictable policy signals paired with coordinated investments across the value chain. D7.3 formulates recommendations across four major levers:

- **Regulatory:** Harmonise EU and national frameworks; set realistic category-specific targets; allow suitable transition periods for R&D; clarify responsibilities along reusable loops; adapt recycled-content rules to functional plastic layers in fibre-based packaging; and simplify VAT and deposit management.
- **Education:** Strengthen EU-wide campaigns explaining reuse and substitution; differentiate clearly between reuse and recycling; increase convenience and product availability to drive behavioural uptake. Provide affordable products.
- **Financial:** Support R&D, industrial adaptation and shared infrastructures; pool investments across sectors; and reward high performers via eco-modulation or similar mechanisms.
- **Standardisation and governance:** Promote packaging and washing standardisation; harmonise technical and hygiene protocols; create cross-sector collaboration frameworks; rethink competition rules to enable collective innovation; and establish a European coordination platform for circular packaging systems.

Overall, the deliverable provides a strategic roadmap for moving from local pilots to interoperable European-scale systems. Only through aligned regulation, shared infrastructure and consistent communication can Europe fulfil the ambitions of the PPWR and achieve an effective shift toward circular packaging.

1. Context and objectives

1.1. European policy landscape

Europe is entering a decisive decade for **transforming its packaging systems towards circularity**. The entry into force of the **Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)** on 11 February 2025 marks a structural turning point in the European transition toward a circular packaging economy. Replacing Directive 94/62/EC, the PPWR shifts from a directive-based framework to a directly applicable regulation, introducing binding, harmonised rules across all Member States from 12 August 2026. Together with the **Single-Use Plastics Directive (EU) 2019/904** and ambitious national frameworks such as **France's AGEC Law** and **Spain's Royal Decree 1055/2022**, it creates an integrated policy environment designed to reduce single-use plastics, scale reuse systems, and deploy recyclable fibre-based packaging where environmentally justified.

This evolving landscape establishes a clear hierarchy of actions: prevention first, reuse as the preferred circular model, and substitution only when compatible with recyclability and positive environmental performance. The AGEC Law initiated this trajectory in 2020, requiring a **20% reduction in single-use plastic packaging by 2025, 50% achieved through reuse**, supported by dedicated decrees structuring obligations by sector and company size. Moreover, in 20240, Article 7 of the AGEC law stipulates that single-use plastics will no longer be marketed.

At EU level, the PPWR introduces reuse obligations for beverage packaging by 2030, while requiring all packaging on the market to meet design-for-reuse and recyclability criteria. **By 2040, the regulation targets a 40% reuse share for beverage packaging and a 15% reduction in packaging waste per member state**, setting an unprecedented long-term ambition.

However, in practice, this policy landscape remains **fragmented and complex**. Member States have introduced parallel national frameworks, such as France’s AGECL law, that diverge in definitions, timelines, and enforcement. For the industry, this results in **regulatory saturation** and uncertainty, discouraging investment in infrastructure and innovation. Actors across the value chain report difficulty aligning their packaging strategies with evolving regulations that are not yet fully harmonised.

Industry stakeholders increasingly call for a **coherent, stable, operational European framework** that sets clear milestones and ensures that environmental ambition is matched by economic and logistical feasibility.

1.2. Market and consumer dynamics

At the same time, consumer expectations are accelerating the demand for visible, verifiable sustainability in packaging. According to the **Amcor “Consumer Claims Packaging Report” (2025)**, **CITEO / Action Plus report “Perception environnementale des emballages” (2021)** and the **“Pro Carton European Packaging Preferences study” (2020)**, several key trends shape the market:

- 84% of consumers check recycling instructions, **making recyclability the most influential packaging claim**.
- **Understanding of sustainability concepts is rising**: 71% understand “recycled materials” (this has risen by 4% since 2022) and 72% understand paper-based packaging claims.
- **70% actively try to reduce plastic use**, and nearly half prefer buying from retailers reducing non-recyclable plastics.
- **Strong preference for paper/cardboard**: 62% say it is better for the environment and 57% find it easier to recycle. Trust in paper is growing, with 18% willing to pay more for paper-based packaging.
- **Reuse is gaining traction**: 24% cite it as a sustainability lever and 17% say it would encourage purchase.

These dynamics indicate that **consumer perception aligns with the policy trajectory**, yet behavioural adoption lags when systems are fragmented or unclear. **The combination of regulation, affordability, and consumer education** will therefore determine the success of the packaging transition, ensuring that the gap between willingness and action is bridged.

1.3. Objectives of deliverable D7.3

The purpose of this deliverable is to **translate R3PACK’s empirical findings into forward-looking policy scenarios** that support European and national decision-makers in designing effective packaging transition strategies for the next years to come.

Specifically, D7.3 will:

1. **Model three “What if” scenarios** that illustrate contrasting futures depending on the consistency of EU and Member State actions, investments in solutions, consumer engagement, and identify the potential impacts of each scenario:
 - *Scenario 1 – Business as usual*
 - *Scenario 2 – Collaborative regional initiatives*
 - *Scenario 3 – Integrated European solutions*

2. **Formulate policy recommendations** across 4 levers to support reusable and paper-based packaging solutions:
 - Regulatory
 - Consumer education
 - Financial
 - Standardisation and governance

Deliverable D7.3 provides a **strategic vision** for policy makers and industry players, linking the lessons learned from R3PACK with the EU's ambitions for the circular economy. It is both a **summary of the lessons learned** and a **navigation tool** for moving from experimentation to implementation.

2. What if scenarios

The **three theoretical scenarios** presented below were developed **based on the findings of the R3PACK project and several studies**. This dual foundation of **theoretical knowledge and practical experience** with the identified levers ensures that the proposed scenarios are as realist as possible.

2.1. Scenarios building based on R3PACK learnings

The **R3PACK project (Grant Agreement No. 101060806)** contributes empirical evidence on two complementary pathways for reducing plastic packaging in the European food sector:

1. **Reuse systems**, tested with major retailers and brands, demonstrating the feasibility and limits of large-scale circular loops (return logistics, washing, standardisation).
2. **Fibre-based substitution**, validating industrially scalable fibre solutions to replace complex plastic multilayer packaging.

The lessons learned and observations made during the R3PACK project have contributed to the development of plausible scenarios for the **large-scale deployment of reuse and substitution solutions** by **highlighting the levers or bottlenecks** presented below.

Technical insights – progress under real constraints

Progress is tangible but varies **depending on the type of product**. Industrial adaptation remains complex, and complete substitution or integration of reuse cannot yet be achieved without further R&D and standardisation.

R3PACK has confirmed that **reuse and fibre substitution are technically feasible** for certain product categories, but **not yet fully developed** for large-scale deployment.

- **In the reuse pillar**, in-store pilot projects at Coopérative U and Carrefour have validated the essential functions (development of standardised packaging between competing manufacturers, implementation of RVM machines, in-store communication, several in-store collections carried out, improvement of the washing protocol). However, work remains to be done on technical obstacles (resin, washing, allergen elimination, improvement of IT tools for invoicing deposits in the reuse loop) and economic obstacles (reducing the operating costs of the loop and the cost of packaging and washing) to optimize the reuse model.
- In the **substitution pillar**, technical feasibility has been demonstrated for several product categories (e.g. pastry dough, savoury biscuits), but for others it has

remained **limited by the machinability and barriers** required by certain products.

- It is therefore necessary to support industrial R&D on high-performance fibre-based materials and compatible high-speed equipment. Processes specifically tailored to paper materials must continue to be developed to bridge the performance and cost gap with plastics, whose processes have been optimised over decades.
- The barrier properties (OTR, WVTR, grease resistance, etc.) of the solutions must also be improved to ensure a shelf-life equivalent to that of conventional plastics for more demanding product categories.

Economic insights – balancing ambitions and economic realities

Cost competitiveness has **not yet been achieved**. A large-scale transition requires **political and financial support** combined with shared infrastructure. Funding for the R3PACK project made it possible to explore reuse and substitution solutions and identify the key levers that need additional funding to one day achieve large-scale deployment of these solutions.

The economic analysis carried out during the demonstration phases revealed that economic feasibility is currently one of the main obstacles to scaling up.

For reuse,

- **The main barrier is the high cost** of purchasing packaging, increased costs of manufacturing and additional reuse-loop related costs (collection, sorting, washing and transport). Today, in R3PACK experiment, **reuse-loop related costs represent the most expensive** components of the reuse system and are the primary barriers to economic viability.
- **An increase in volume and return rate are essential.** A significant increase in volumes placed on the market, combined with high consumer participation and return rates, will optimise washing, sorting, and transport operations and to reduce unit costs.
- **Importance of standardisation and collective approach:** Packaging standardisation across manufacturers enables the optimisation of sorting, washing and logistics, increases reuse rates, and overall accelerates cost optimisation. Moreover, shared infrastructures are key enablers to lowering costs and improving overall system efficiency.
- **Deposits can play a key economic role.** They must motivate returns without discouraging purchase, generally remaining below €1. Consumers intuitively expect reuse to cost less than single use thanks to competitive prices or deposit refunds.

For fibre-based substitution,

- **The main barrier is the high material cost:** paper packaging remains 2–5 times more expensive than plastic.
- **Reducing this gap requires economies of scale,** improved industrial efficiency and targeted investment.
- **Switching to paper currently slows production by up to 20%,** requiring CAPEX for new machinery or retrofits.
- **Fiscal pressure** through rising EPR fees, environmental taxes and PPWR requirements, **will gradually increase the cost of single-use plastics,** improving the competitiveness of paper-based alternatives while keeping in mind that the cost of paper may also change favourably or unfavourably.
- **Public funding is essential to support R&D and equipment upgrades.**
- **Commercially, the higher cost of paper erodes margins** (up to 45% for some products) **and complicates adoption for consumer for a higher cost.**

Behavioural insights – awareness without established consumption habits

The behavioural readiness exists, but it **depends on the clarity of messages and the ease of use of solutions**. Education and harmonised communication are prerequisites for mass participation.

Scaling reuse systems requires strong consumer understanding, clear visibility, and high convenience.

- **Confusion is a major barrier:** only 3 in 10 consumers spontaneously distinguish reuse from recycling, highlighting the need for large-scale education and improvements in user experience design.
- Consumers show a strong interest in the topic of reuse. 70% of the 14,000 consumers interviewed in stores were receptive to arguments in favour of reuse.
- **Visibility is equally critical:** clear signage, unified reuse logos and well-positioned RVMs significantly increase return rates.
- **Simplicity and consistency of messages help avoid fragmentation.**
- **Convenience drives habit formation:** consumers expect a broad and familiar assortment and returns stabilise after several months as habits form. The purchasing and return process must be simple, and the act of reuse must be 'almost unique and uniform,' as explained in the study 'Packaging and Reuse: Challenges, Opportunities and Prospects' by the National Packaging Council (2024).
- **Economic expectations also play a role:** many consumers assume reusable products should be cheaper, and deposits of €0.50–€0.80 yield the highest return rates though convenience often outweighs financial incentives. Home delivery operators using a deposit system report high return rates, between 80% and 97% according to the study 'Towards an economic barometer for the bulk and reuse sector', Réseau Vrac et Réemploi (2024).

Scaling fibre-based packaging hinges on perceived quality, functionality and category-specific requirements.

- **Consumers prioritise product protection and ease of use;** paper is perceived as fragile for liquids or semi-liquids.
- **Transparency is a major barrier for fresh products** where visual assessment is essential for consumers, limiting acceptance of opaque paper solutions.
- **Price tolerance exists for small premiums,** but not for significant cost increases, making optimisation essential. According to the Amcor "Consumer Claims Packaging Report" (2025), only 18% of European consumers say they are willing to pay more for paper-based packaging.
- **Adoption is strongest for dry goods** and produce where transparency matters less.
- **Clear communication on recyclability and end-of-life** is necessary to avoid confusion with compostable or bio-based materials.

Governance insights – fragmented systems and coordination gaps

Scaling reuse and fibre-based substitution requires strong coordination, shared rules and interoperable systems. Across all pilots, appointing a **neutral coordinator** proved essential to align all the value chain actors (manufacturers, retailers, packaging suppliers, washers, logistics operators, ...). A collaborative governance framework enables joint **problem-solving, co-design of solutions and transparent definition of roles and responsibilities**.

For Reuse,

- **Standardised packaging formats** are a major enabler: they enable knowledge to be pooled **during pilot phases** and, on a larger scale, **development costs to**

be shared, the logistics loop to be optimised and, as a result, the associated **costs and environmental impact of the model to be reduced significantly.**

- At a more global system level, reuse requires **harmonised cross-border management:** deposit flows, VAT flows, unified labelling and common technical specifications for reusable packaging.

For fibre-based substitution, standardisation focuses on performance and regulatory clarity.

- Harmonised recyclability tests and end-of-life protocols (e.g., CEPI, Aticelca) are necessary to validate designs and secure acceptance by EPR schemes.
- **Technical standards** for barrier performance, machinability and durability must be aligned to support industrial deployment.

2.2. Scenarios descriptions and impacts

By adjusting the degrees of effort into the parameters listed below, three scenarios have been proposed:

- availability of reusable and fibre-based packaging for manufacturers,
- achieving regulatory objectives,
- educating and engaging consumers,
- financial support
- cooperation – Collective approach

The three studied scenarios have been created based on a European scope with a time horizon of 2035-2040.

Variable parameters	Scenario 1 – Business as Usual	Scenario 2 – Collaborative regional initiatives	Scenario 3 – Fully integrated European solutions
Reuse market share*	5%	15–20%	30-40%
Fibre based market share*	10–15%	20-25%	30-45%
Availability of reusable and fibre-based packaging for manufacturers	<p><u>Fibre-based:</u> Limited number of product categories due to technical constraints</p> <p><u>Reuse:</u> Limited availability of reusable packaging and limited number of product categories available</p> <p>Low producer engagement due to</p>	<p><u>Fibre-based:</u> Increase in the supply of fibre-based packaging and increase of product categories addressed</p> <p><u>Reuse:</u> Several packaging standards are emerging in addition to the reusable packaging already available</p>	<p><u>Fibre-based:</u> The packaging range is very comprehensive and offers numerous solutions with a high paper content</p> <p><u>Reuse:</u> Numerous packaging standards based on different materials coexist</p>

	high purchase and production cost		
Regulatory (EU and national)	Fragmented European and national regulations	EU-led enforcement	Achievement of regulatory objectives
Education and communication on sustainable packaging	Fragmented communications Low consumer engagement due to confusion, lack of knowledge and high cost	Collaborative campaigns Moderate consumer engagement (informed and compliant)	Harmonisation of communication messages Full consumer engagement (new habits integrated)
Financial support	Expensive pilot projects, low return on investment	Public and private investment in R&D and infrastructure	Economically viable model on a large scale
Cooperation – Collective approach	Individual initiatives conducting to specific solution	Solutions developed by players in the same sector covering several product categories Few mutualized packagings are emerging due to collaborative approach	Cooperation and mutualisation between sectors and between actors in the value chain Technical and hygiene standards are defined and applied by all Reuse: packaging used is largely standardised

Summary table of the three scenarios for the development of sustainable packaging solutions

**Schematic illustration of market shares according to different types of packaging*

2.2.1. Scenario 1 - Business as usual

Reuse remains limited ($\approx 5\%$) and fibre-based substitution modest ($\approx 10\text{--}15\%$), with most fibre-based solutions still at R&D stage and reusable packaging scarcely available. Regulations stay fragmented, slowing investment and scaling. Consumers remain confused and disengaged, while pilot projects remain costly with low returns. Technical and commercial testing is sporadic, keeping the market largely dependent on single-use plastics.

Implications of the scenario for reuse

- Very limited market penetration, with pilots remaining small-scale and economically fragile.
- Washing, logistics, IT and deposit systems remain fragmented, preventing efficient loops and keeping costs high.
- Packaging availability remains low, with few standardised formats and high technical uncertainty, especially for plastics.
- Retailer uptake stays marginal: few products are listed, return rates remain unstable and consumer confusion persists.
- Reuse remains dependent on subsidies and cannot compete with single-use economics.

Implications of the scenario for paper-based packaging solutions

- Substitution remains restricted to a few niche products that already show acceptable machinability and shelf-life (e.g. pastry dough, some savoury biscuits).
- Most categories remain blocked due to cost (2–5× plastic), insufficient barriers and reduced production speed.
- No significant industrial investment in paper-dedicated machinery; reliance on existing plastic-oriented lines limits progress.
- Retail deployment is rare, as manufacturers cannot absorb margin loss and retailers lack confidence in consumer acceptance.
- Innovation stays slow as regulatory uncertainty (PPWR) discourages commitments.

2.2.2. Scenario 2 - Collaborative regional initiatives

Reuse market share grows to 15–20% and paper-based solutions to 20–25% thanks to increased supply and emerging cross-sector standards. Public and private investment support the deployment of infrastructure, while joint communication campaigns improve consumer understanding and compliance. EU-level alignment begins to reduce regulatory barriers. Collaboration across the value chain accelerates both substitution and the maturation of reuse systems.

Implications of the scenario for reuse

- Coordinated ecosystem enables moderate deployment (15–20% market share).
- Shared standards emerge (e.g. standardised packaging, common logo and messages on labels, shared washing requirements), improving quality and reducing operational friction. The quality of the wash meets the standards.
- Logistics partially harmonised across several retailers; washing becomes more frequent thanks to higher volumes. IT developments to make ERP and deposit invoicing compatible for manufacturers and distributors may continue.
- Consumer engagement improves thanks to unified communication, leading to higher and quicker return-rate stabilisation.

- Public and private investment is enabling the model to scale up. The economic situation is gradually improving thanks to increased volumes, although it remains sensitive to consumer behaviour.

Implications of the scenario for paper-based packaging solutions

- Collaborative R&D helps manufacturers optimise machinability and sealing parameters; more product categories become viable.
- Joint industrial trials enable broader validation: more biscuits, low-fat snacks and ambient categories are being rolled out.
- Costs remain higher than plastics, but shared investment and improved knowledge transfer reduce the gap.
- Retailers begin listing selected fibre-based SKUs when shelf-life and barrier performance are validated.
- Regulatory alignment efforts accelerate development of compliant high-paper-ratio materials.

2.2.3. Scenario 3 - Fully integrated European solutions

The market shifts toward **large-scale transformation**: reuse reaches 30-40% and paper-based solutions 30-45%. **A comprehensive range of high-paper-content packaging and fully standardised reusable formats coexist** under harmonised EU rules. Consumers integrate **new habits**, and business models become **economically viable at scale**. Coordinated governance and shared infrastructure enable widespread substitution of single-use plastics across all studied markets.

Implications of the scenario for reuse

- Reuse becomes structurally embedded in the market (30-40%).
- Full standardisation of formats, washing protocols, allergen management and traceability ensure high reliability and low variability.
- Harmonised EU deposit system and interoperable IT remove major administrative barriers.
- Industrial washing infrastructures scale across regions, enabling the establishment of short, cost-efficient, high-throughput circuits for all reusable packaging.
- After an initial period marked by significant financial support to ignite industrialisation of reuse, it is no longer necessary to subsidise reuse thanks to economies of scale. The model becomes viable thanks to the large volumes of packaging placed on the market. Retailers fully integrate reuse in operations, with a large and familiar assortment driving automatic consumer adoption and stable return cycles.

Implications of the scenario for paper-based packaging solutions

- Broad industrial shift toward high-performance fibre-based packaging, including improved barrier technologies suitable for more demanding categories.
- Dedicated high-speed paper-oriented machinery becomes widespread, reducing production costs and improving efficiency.
- Fibre-based solutions become competitive for many dry and semi-dry products, with transparent or high-barrier innovations enabling uptake in more sensitive categories.
- Harmonised PPWR requirements secure investment and accelerate market adoption.
- Retailers adopt fibre-based solutions at scale, supported by robust consumer acceptance and clear sustainability communication. However, it should be noted that certain product categories seem more suited to reuse than paper substitution, or even impossible to substitute due to their specificity (ex: specific production process such as vacuum-sealed) (see more detail in the Policy recommendations section and D5.3).

3. Policy recommendations

Through the R3PACK project, packaging reuse and substitution solutions were tested on a small scale. This made it possible to identify the levers that need to be implemented to enable their large-scale deployment, which is necessary for the widespread adoption and profitability of the model. The following recommendations will enable progress towards ambitious scenarios described above.

Large-scale deployment therefore requires **coherent political action** on four interdependent levers that have been identified:

1. **Regulatory (EU and national)** to provide direction and stability
2. **Education and communication** to ensure consumer participation
3. **Financial** to enable investment and innovation
4. **Standardisation and governance** to achieve interoperability and trust

The following recommendations summarise the key enablers identified through R3PACK's work packages, pilot feedback, and policy review.

They are categorised in 3 types: REUSE / SUBSTITUTION / BOTH. Depending on the application perimeter.

3.1. Regulatory lever

The transition to reusable packaging solutions and cellulose-based packaging is strongly encouraged by regulations that provide a framework for the development of these solutions and encourage their widespread adoption. This framework must be well thought out and in line with national regulations to be effective.

BOTH: Set ambitious but realistic targets by product category

Each product category, material and type of solution (reuse and substitution) have advantages and disadvantages depending on the product-packaging combination considered. There is no single packaging solution that can be applied to all product categories. Even if substitution solution can address multiple food categories, reuse seems more relevant for liquids such as juice, water, or syrup than fibre-based solution. The targets set must consider the actual technical constraints of the product to be both ambitious and realistic or consider exemption when justified. Targets must distinguish between categories where solutions are beneficial to the environment (e.g. for reuse: glass-bottled drinks, etc.) and those where they are not (e.g. for reuse: lightweight flexible films).

Suggested means of implementation:

- Conduct case studies/roadmaps by sector to tailor targets
- Conduct 'macro' LCA and impact analysis for each packaging-product combination that can be used by the entire sector to ensure that the packaging change has a beneficial environmental impact compared to the current packaging.

BOTH: Harmonise between the EU and countries, simplify and aim for regulatory and reporting efficiency

Industrial players need long-term visibility to invest in reuse and substitution solutions. The coexistence of regulatory frameworks at European (PPWR) and national level creates uncertainty that slows down decision-making and can even lead to deadlock for manufacturers.

This regulatory harmonisation between Europe and the various European countries, aligning with common measures in terms of scope, objectives and duration, is essential to accelerate the deployment of these new solutions.

For example, in France, the AGECE law sets a target of 10% reused packaging (units) across all product categories by 2027, and the PPWR sets a target of 40% reused packaging for beverages.

Common definitions and indicators should be implemented through delegated acts under the PPWR.

Measures should be as simple as possible, harmonised and implemented at a macroeconomic level in order to ease the burden on economic actors and thus encourage and simplify compliance.

BOTH: Allow sufficient time for R&D and the implementation of solutions

Europe's ambitious targets are helping to mobilise economic players on these issues of reuse and substitution. However, ambitious objectives can result in tight deadlines that overlook the current Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) of reuse and substitution solutions. These technologies require time, not only to advance and scale, but also to be integrated into logistical, economic, and accounting models and to gain consumer acceptance. Setting regulatory milestones in line with operational deadlines and actual R&D times would provide the most appropriate support to economic actors.

For instance, within the reuse part of R3PACK project, the development of standardized, reusable packaging suitable for experimental deployment required a minimum of two years. This timeframe would need to be further extended when aiming to design packaging solutions shared among more industrial stakeholders. In addition, the packaging solutions developed under R3PACK still require further optimisation, notably regarding plastic resin selection and the development of robust reusable closing systems.

On substitution, research and innovation activities from early-stage development (TRL 1-2) to market deployment (TRL 8-9), typically require up to ten years. R3PACK's work on substitution started at TRL 2 and, following one year of development, structured itself into two parallel work streams:

- a longer-term research pathway continuing the development of fibre-based packaging solutions with high bio-based content and paper ratio, recyclability and even compostability end-of-life, reaching TRL 4-5 by the end of the project. At least additional 6 years are required to continue until reaching TRL 8-9.
- a short-term pathway addressing more mature paper-based solutions (TRL 5-6) that already approach the barrier and sealing requirements of food manufacturers, despite still containing a significant amount of petroleum-based materials and not covering all product categories, for validation on industrial lines and in-store deployment (TRL 7-8).

Furthermore, industrial implementation of solution developed necessitates the adaptation and improvement of existing manufacturing equipment to meet the challenges associated with cellulose fibre. Where further machine development is required, this industrial adaptation phase may take an additional two to five years, depending on the product category, to achieve the rates obtained on plastic packaging.

SUBSTITUTION: Defining the 'right amount of plastic' to functionalise paper-based packaging

Today, developing fibre-based packaging for food applications still requires a thin functional layer of plastic, typically 10 to 25% of the total structure to ensure barrier performance, safety and machinability. However, these functional layers are currently unable to incorporate recycled content, due to technical and regulatory constraints.

Under the current PPWR, any packaging containing more than 5% plastic must comply with recycled-content requirements. This means that most emerging fibre-based solutions are automatically considered non-compliant, even when they reduce plastic use by 70–90% compared to conventional packaging.

To avoid blocking innovation, the 5% threshold could either be revised (for functional layers) according to innovations and sector specifications or made gradual through a transitional exemption aligned with realistic R&D timelines.

REUSE: Allow time for reuse to emerge before imposing reincorporation targets

Through the R3PACK experiment, PP has been tested, and challenges remain regarding the use of PP resin for reuse. Reusable plastic packaging still requires R&D work to identify or develop the most suitable resin.

Today, in the reuse market, two plastic resins are mainly used in reusable packaging: PP and Tritan. While PP is recyclable, recycled PP is not yet suitable for food contact. On the other hand, Tritan remains very expensive and there is currently no recycling chain for Tritan.

Before imposing reincorporation targets for reusable plastic, efforts should first be made to develop and identify a plastic resin suitable for reuse. The current reality regarding reusable plastic resin must be confronted with regulatory requirements.

REUSE: Sharing and clarifying responsibilities and obligations along the value chain

In a packaging reuse loop, packaging passes through numerous actors in the value chain, multiplying risks and complicating the allocation of responsibilities. Clarifying these notions of risk and responsibility is essential for scaling reuse and should be addressed through open, collaborative dialogue.

Furthermore, the transition to reusable packaging solutions affects all players in the value chain from packaging manufacturers to industrials and retailers, as well as washers, etc. This may require organisational changes and, as a result, new obligations and responsibilities for each actor of the value chain. Clarity on each other's roles, responsibility and obligations will help scale reuse.

REUSE: Simplify and harmonise VAT (or other taxation) management for reusable packaging billing

The R3PACK experiment highlighted the challenges associated with billing for reuse. Indeed, implementing a reusable system involves modifying the usual billing system and VAT management for reusable packaging.

First, adding a deposit line to a product invoice requires IT developments. In addition, the management of VAT on reusable packaging presents challenges as some regulations (ex: in France) lack of clarity and specification by product category. VAT management should be harmonised between European countries and clarified when needed.

Moreover, a potential policy measure to be further assessed is the reduction or elimination of value-added tax (VAT) on environmentally sustainable products, with the objective of narrowing the competitiveness gap with conventional single-use plastic packaging.

3.2. Education lever

Reusable packaging solutions and cellulose-based packaging can disrupt consumer habits and in-store staff tasks. Clear, transparent and motivational communication is required for the model to be adopted.

BOTH: Build trust in these solutions through communication campaigns

Consumers are more likely to adopt circular packaging (reuse and substitution solutions) when they understand its benefits. The EU and countries should communicate widely about the advantages of these solutions to encourage consumers to adopt these new consumption habits and cultivate new behavioural norms.

REUSE: Clarify the difference between reuse and recycling

Consumer research in R3PACK shows persistent confusion between both concepts. Clear communication on reuse system and its difference with recycling should be implemented across Europe. Common icons, consistent wording, and visible examples in retail environments can help consumer better understand reuse and improve return rates.

REUSE: Increasing convenience and expanding the range of reusable products

Adoption increases when consumers perceive reuse as an “easy” gesture. Policies should therefore encourage retailers to **expand the range of reusable products** and provide accessible collection points.

The R3PACK experiment showed that the second biggest barrier preventing consumers from switching to reuse is the lack of their usual products being available for reuse. Increasing the range of reusable products is mandatory to engage more consumers.

3.3. Financial lever

The current shift towards sustainable packaging represents a significant change and costs for players in the value chain. Industries need financial support to transition towards sustainable packaging.

BOTH: Provide financial aid to support R&D and investment in industrial tools in these new value chains

The implementation of large-scale funding programmes, such as those under Horizon Europe, is essential to support actors that transition towards reuse and substitution packaging. Financial support is needed across the whole value chain to reduce the high R&D costs, enable industrial adaptation and the development of raw materials for cellulosic packaging solutions and logistics.

BOTH: Promote the pooling of investments

Reuse and substitution solutions require massive investment to scale. Promoting the pooling of costs through the development of standards, industrial infrastructure (e.g. creation of co-packing hubs) and shared innovation implemented at regional level, etc. would reduce the financial burden on each player in the value chain and streamline costs.

BOTH: Financially reward sustained efforts

Financially supporting the value chain also involves rewarding good performers who make efforts to comply with the law and participate in projects that enable the development of these solutions on a large scale. The principle of eco-modulation can help encourage frontrunners to sustain their efforts while motivating others to join the transition.

SUBSTITUTION: Funding Research Projects on Alternative Biomass-Based Fibres

As demand for paper-based packaging increases, the long-term availability of wood-derived cellulose could become limited, thereby jeopardizing forest resources. Investments should therefore fund research projects focused on alternatives to wood-based fibres derived from biomass (e.g., agricultural by-products) and on improving fibre recovery yields in recycling processes.

These investments are essential to secure the supply of raw materials, reduce pressure on resources, and enhance the circularity and resilience of paper-based packaging systems.

3.4. Standardisation and governance lever

To accelerate the adoption of these new packaging solutions, it is essential to support their standardisation, comply with existing regulatory and food-safety standards, and establish new ones where needed.

BOTH: Create a list of available sustainable packaging (reuse and fibre based) on the market

An inventory of sustainable packaging solutions currently available on the market would highlight packaging and suppliers offering alternatives to single-use paper packaging. This would make it easier for manufacturers to switch to using these solutions.

REUSE: Promote national or European standardised packaging

When reusable packaging is standardised, it reduces development costs and enhances logistical efficiency. This optimisation strengthens both the profitability and the environmental performance of the reuse model. Cross-manufacturer packaging standardisation is therefore a critical lever for scaling reuse.

BOTH: Define common technical and hygiene standards

REUSE: Establishing a Europe-wide validated protocol for washing glass and plastic packaging would ensure a consistent, accepted quality standard across the EU. Developing these common technical and hygiene standards to certify compliant washing processes still requires further R&D and investment.

SUBSTIT: Simultaneously, efforts must clarify performance criteria for barriers in fibre-based packaging to secure regulatory approval for food contact applications.

BOTH: Create frameworks for collaboration

The creation of frameworks for cross-sector collaboration (e.g. between agri-food and cosmetics) and between all actors in the value chain and sectors (suppliers, machine operators, manufacturers, logistics providers, wholesalers, distributors) promotes cross-sector cooperation. For example, in the agri-food sector, there are large

volumes but little money available to invest in these new solutions, whereas the opposite is true for the cosmetics sector. These cooperation frameworks can be implemented with the aim of pooling efforts, investments and knowledge.

BOTH: Rethinking competition law in an environmental context that requires collaboration rather than competition

The challenge of environmental transition requires revolutions in R&D, usage, technologies, infrastructure, and marketing. The revolution in resources and materials, doing better with what we have, and shifting from linear to circular models often takes place on a large scale and requires action within the entire value chain and even between competitors. The authorities responsible for enforcing competition law at the EU and Member State levels have already addressed these issues: how to regulate collaborations? How to protect consumers and their benefits? (Green Deal, revision of the exemption regulation, etc.)

This work must be consolidated, accelerated, and operationalized to produce a very clear, agile, and responsive framework.

Failing this, we will not make the transition, and we will not create green industries on a European scale.

In France in particular, the authority states on its website:

"Sustainable development issues are now playing an increasingly important role in litigation, consultation and merger control, particularly with regard to the examination of new markets. They are also emerging in the support offered by the Authority as part of its 'open door' policy, which allows actors involved in the transition to consult it in advance on their projects."

<https://www.autoritedelaconurrence.fr/fr/developpement-durable-et-concurrence-une-combinaison-qui-progresse>

BOTH: Establish a European coordination platform

In these innovation projects, which unite many participants over the long term, a coordinator is essential to ensure collaboration.

A European platform dedicated to packaging circularity could oversee interoperability between national systems, data collection and dialogue between stakeholders.

3.5. Policy recommendations conclusion

Circular packaging will only scale through **coordinated action across these four levers**. Regulation defines the direction, finance builds the capacity, education creates acceptance, and standardisation secures interoperability and cost efficiency. Together, they provide the foundation for Europe to **move from experimentation to large scale implementation**.

4. Conclusion

Deliverable D7.3 shows that Europe's shift toward circular packaging hinges on the combined success of reuse systems and fibre-based substitution, two complementary pathways to reduce single-use plastics. Insights from the R3PACK demonstrations confirm that technically viable solutions already exist but are hindered by fragmented regulations, limited industrial readiness, insufficient shared infrastructure, and uneven consumer awareness. Scaling these solutions will require coordinated efforts across regulatory, financial, behavioural, and governance levers.

The three scenarios developed in this deliverable illustrate the consequences of inaction versus structured cooperation. A "business as usual" trajectory would reinforce fragmentation and keep reuse and substitution at niche levels, while collaborative regional initiatives could unlock moderate progress through shared standards and joint investment. Only a fully integrated European approach, marked by harmonised regulation, interoperability, standardised packaging, and consistent communication achieves the scale needed to make sustainable packaging economically viable and environmentally impactful.

The policy recommendations outlined in D7.3 provide a coherent framework to transition from experimentation to systemic implementation. Harmonized targets, realistic timelines, robust support for R&D and industrial adaptation, cross-sector collaboration, and a dedicated European coordination platform emerge as essential enablers. Together, these measures can offer industry clarity, foster consumer trust, and create the conditions necessary for high-performing reuse and fibre-based solutions to thrive.

Ultimately, the findings of R3PACK highlight that Europe has a unique opportunity to accelerate packaging sustainability by aligning ambition with operational feasibility. Deliverable D7.3 offers a forward-looking roadmap to guide policy makers, industry and civil society in building a resilient, scalable and sustainable packaging ecosystem.

